

Date of publication: March 2, 2023

DOI: 10.52270/26585561_2023_17_19_66

Historical Sciences

FEATURES OF TRAINING STUDENTS IN THE FIELD OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS IN TECHNICAL UNIVERSITIES OF RUSSIA: HISTORICAL ASPECTS

Lubkin, Yanis Yanovich¹, Nikiforova, Lyubov Alexandrovna², Ermolova, Elena Anatolievna³, Gruza, Maria Sergeevna⁴, Balakari, Tatyana Mikhailovna⁵

¹Senior Lecturer, Voronezh State Technical University, 84, 20-letiya Oktyabrya Street, Voronezh, Russia, E-mail: ia.iani4@yandex.ru

²Senior Lecturer, Voronezh State Technical University, 84, 20 years of October Street, Voronezh, Russia, E-mail: nikiforovala@inbox.ru

³Senior Lecturer, Voronezh State Technical University, 84, 20 years of October Street, Voronezh, Russia, E-mail: fizcult_kaf@vgasu.vrn.ru

⁴Senior Lecturer, Voronezh State Technical University, 84, 20-letiya Oktyabrya Street, Voronezh, Russia, E-mail: mgruza@yandex.ru

⁵Senior Lecturer, Voronezh State Technical University, 84, 20-letiya Oktyabrya Street, Voronezh, Russia, E-mail: malya.tanya@mail.ru

Abstract

The article discusses the system of higher professional education in the field of physical culture and sports, which is far from being able to fully provide the economy with specialists capable of effectively carrying out professional activities in market conditions. Specialists after graduating from the university should have not only fundamental versatile knowledge, skills and abilities in the professional field, but also a set of stable properties that determine suitability for professional activities and meet the requirements of modern production, such as stress resistance, competitiveness, high performance, self-defense, health and range functionality of the body. It is these qualities that can be formed in the process of physical education, since when playing sports, situations are created that make one act more meaningfully and restrainedly.

Keywords: sport, education, student, university, history, country.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the most crucial period of the life of young people, it is necessary to provide the opportunity to acquire knowledge, skills and abilities in the field of physical education, offered both within the framework of the state educational program, and considered in the aspect of preparation for professional activity, since the level of formation of the motivational-need sphere of the individual is recognized as a system-forming factor in the field of professional activity of a specialist and preparation for its implementation.

As is known, the conditions for the implementation of professional activities by university graduates have various features that must be taken into account in the process of preparing students for future professional activities. However, the physical education of students within the discipline "Physical culture" cannot fully solve all the problems related to the physical training of future specialists and physical education at the university, built in the traditional way, unfortunately, cannot help meet the requirements of employers. Therefore, it is necessary to improve educational programs, develop new pedagogical technologies, introduce into the upbringing and educational process more capacious physical education programs that are able to ensure the preparation and success of future professional activities.

II. METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of the study is based on the historical interpretation of the universal connection and interdependence of processes and phenomena, activity as a way of self-realization in work and communication; philosophical propositions about objective trends in the development of society and science, about the relationship between content and form, historical and logical in pedagogical knowledge; an integrated approach that combines theoretical and practical issues of various sciences (pedagogy, psychology, general and age physiology, valeology, sports medicine, etc.); theories of professional activity; psychological and pedagogical theory and the concept of the process of professional and life development of the individual.

III. RESULTS

In order to determine the principles and measures of state support for university sports, its status and place in the physical culture and sports movement of the country, it is necessary to adopt a federal law "On student sports in the Russian Federation". The law will establish the social, legal, economic and organizational foundations for the activities of state bodies, public organizations, higher educational institutions in the field of university sports in the Russian Federation.

Pedagogical management of the development of sports in universities involves the coordination of the activities of state authorities at various levels (federal, subjects of the federation, local) and higher educational institutions to create regulatory, financial and organizational conditions for sports. The development of these conditions will determine the degree of success of students in sports and the gradual improvement of students' sports skills specifically for each university. For the purpose of the pedagogical management of the development of student sports at the federal level, it is necessary to: more actively use the capabilities of the scientific and methodological council for physical culture of the Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation to monitor compliance with the requirements of the federal component (in terms of implementation by universities) of the state educational standard of the discipline "Physical Education".

In order to analyze and optimize the processes of physical education and development of sports among students in the universities of the country, it is necessary to introduce the practice of annual reports of physical education departments and sports clubs of universities, which submit to the scientific and methodological council for physical culture of the Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation, student sports development programs in the regions and universities (the largest). It is necessary, taking into account the competence, to establish: the program and regulatory framework for the development of student sports in universities, including time standards, the principles of material support for student athletes (sports scholarships), conditions for admission to state universities of high-class athletes, indicators characterizing the success (rating) of universities in development sports among students, as well as the requirements for sports facilities and the provision of physical education departments with sports equipment for the training process.

Support for elite sports at the level of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation should be carried out with the involvement of budgetary funds with the annual approval of state social orders for the training of the strongest athletes in higher educational institutions that implement training programs for highly qualified athletes in the regions.

Local government authorities should make greater use of tax incentives for universities in mutual offsets for utility and other payments, as well as provide universities with municipal sports facilities free of charge in cases where they implement municipal sports programs.

The sports life of students in an educational institution largely depends on the activities of an intra-university public organization - a sports club. The administration and the department of physical education provide him with possible material, methodological and practical assistance both in the work of individual sports sections and groups, and in the organization of competitions.

A significant role in the organization of interuniversity sports competitions is played by the public association of students and employees of higher educational institutions - the Russian Student Sports Union and its regional organizations.

Its Charter states that the main goal of the Union is to consolidate the efforts of all interested organizations in the development of physical culture and health work, student sports, the harmonization of physical and spiritual education, the health of students in higher educational institutions and the preparation of athletes for participation in competitions at various levels. Based on the results of student sports competitions held by the Union, the composition of the student team for all-Russian and international sports competitions is determined.

The International Student Conference, convened after the end of the First World War at the initiative of the French athlete Jean Petitjean, established the World University Sports Games for the first time. The first competitions were held in 1924 in Warsaw in three sports: athletics, swimming, fencing.

World War II interrupted the World University Sports Games. In the period before World War II, Soviet athletes did not participate in these competitions, since Soviet student sports organizations were not allowed to work with the International University Sports Federation (FISU).

For the first time in student competitions, Soviet athletes performed in 1957 in Paris, when the World Student Sports Games were held in honor of the 100th anniversary of the organization of the university in France. Soviet athletes who were not yet members of FISU participated in these competitions. In 1959, the meeting of the International University Sports Federation, which met in Turin (Italy), accepted into its ranks the student organizations of the socialist countries.

Mass sports give millions of people the opportunity to improve their physical and motor abilities, improve their health and prolong creative longevity, resist the undesirable effects on the body of modern production and everyday life conditions.

The purpose of practicing various types of mass sports is to improve health, improve physical development, fitness and active recreation. This is due to the solution of a number of specific tasks: to increase the functionality of individual body systems, to correct physical development and physique, to increase general and professional performance, to master life skills and abilities, to have a good time.

The tasks of mass sports largely repeat the tasks of physical culture, but are realized by the sports orientation of regular classes and training. A significant part of the youth belongs to the elements of mass sports.

Along with mass sports, there is the sport of the highest achievements, or big sport. The goal of big sport is fundamentally different from the goal of mass sports. This is the achievement of the highest sports results or victory at major sporting events. Any highest achievement of an athlete is not only of personal importance, but becomes the property of the state, since records and victories in major international competitions contribute to strengthening the country's authority on the world stage.

Today, elite sport is the only activity model in which the functioning of almost all body systems of outstanding champions can manifest itself in the zone of absolute physiological and mental limits of a healthy person. This allows not only to penetrate the secrets of the maximum human capabilities, but also to determine the ways of rational development and use of the natural abilities that each person has in his professional and social activities, increasing overall performance.

By decision of the FISU General Assembly, the World University Sports Games are held every two years: every odd year - summer, every even year - winter. The games were called the Universiade. During the Universiade, FISU adheres unswervingly to the Olympic ideals, the competitions are held as holidays for the student youth of our planet. They serve to expand international sports relations, strengthen international friendship, mutual understanding between students from all over the world.

IV. CONCLUSION

The success of a higher educational institution in the pedagogical management of the development of student sports depends on the creation of conditions and the provision of opportunities for students to choose the right to engage in sports, depending on the level of their sports qualifications and the development of regulatory documents governing the sports activities of universities: "Regulations on the Universiade of the university", "On the status student-athlete of the university", "On the sports scholarship of the university", competition "Best coach", "Best athlete of the university", "On the rating of faculties for sports work among students", "On the priorities of spending extra-budgetary funds of the university", "On the sports budget of the university".

The Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation and the Russian Student Sports Union, together with the State Committee for Physical Culture, Sports and Tourism, need to organize a summing up of the activities of the authorized structures of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation, municipalities and higher educational institutions in the development of student sports.

REFERENCE LIST

- Andrews, D.K. (1993) The role of education in promoting a healthy lifestyle in the twenty-first century. Theory and practice of physical culture. Number 1. Pp. 46-48. (In Russ).
- Balsevich V.K. (1988) Physical culture for everyone and for everyone. M.: Physical culture and sport. 208 p. (In Russ).
- Cherkashin V.P. (2000) Individualization of the training process of young athletes in speed and power athletics: Monograph: VGAFK. 240 p. (In Russ).
- Erofeeva T.M. (1995) Physical culture in the educational process of the university. Physical culture: upbringing, education, training. Pp. 27-35. (In Russ).
- Ershov B.A., Lubkin Y.Y. (2016) The activities of the Russian Orthodox Church in countering extremism and terrorism in modern Russia. Historical, philosophical, political and legal sciences, cultural studies and art history. Questions of theory and practice. Vol. 11-2 (73). Pp. 97-99. (In Russ).
- Ershov B.A., Nebolsin V.A., Solovieva S.R. (2020) Higher education in technical universities of Russia. 7th International conference on education and social sciences. Abstracts Proceedings. Pp. 55-58. (In Engl).
- Ershov B.A., Perepelitsyn A., Glazkov E., Volkov I., Volkov S. (2019) Church and state in Russia: management issues. 5th International conference on advances in education and social sciences. Abstracts & Proceedings, e-publication. Pp. 26-29. (In Engl).
- Ershov B.A., Zhdanova T.A., Kashirsky S.N., Monko T. (2020) Education in the university as an important factor in the socialization of students in Russia. 6th International Conference on Advances in Education. Abstracts & Proceedings. Pp. 517-520. (In Engl).
- Fomin Y.A., Vavilov Yu.I. (1991) Physiological foundations of motor activity. M.: Physical culture and sport. 224 p. (In Russ).
- Fursov V.N., Ershov B.A., Lubkin Y.Y. (2016) The participation of the Russian Orthodox Church in the patriotic education of the young generation in modern Russia. News of the Voronezh State Pedagogical University. Vol. 1 (270). Pp. 147-150. (In Russ).
- Gessen S.I. (1995) Worldview and education. Education and pedagogy of the Russian abroad. M. 105 p. (In Russ).
- Gladkikh O.V., Ermolova E.A., Lukin A.A., Ermilova O.Y., Vasilyeva L.M. Physical Culture and Health-Improving Movement in the USSR in 1920-1930. Bulletin Social-Economic and Humanitarian Research. Tom 12, Issue 14. Pp. 37 - 43. (In Engl).
- Gruga M.S., Vyalykh N.N., Dushkin O.A., Shcherbina I.V., Nikiforova L.A. (2022) Historical aspects of sports-mass work in higher educational institutions of Russia. Bulletin Social-Economic and Humanitarian Research. Vol. 13 (15). Pp. 3-9. (In Engl).
- Ignatiev A.S., Lotonenko A.V. (1999) Theoretical and methodological aspects of physical culture of students. Voronezh. 168 p. (In Russ).
- Jusudov V.P. (2000) Motor modes in the rehabilitation system: A manual on physical therapy for students of the faculty, stomatol. fac. and fac. sports. medicine. St. Petersburg. 115 p. (In Russ).
- Kuramshin Yu.F. (1996) Higher sports achievements as an object of system analysis. St. Petersburg: GAFK named after P.F. Lesgaft. 169 p. (In Russ).
- Lubkin Y.Y., Novikov Y.N., Gostev V.N., Kutuzova I. A., Balakari T.M. (2022) The Development of Physical Culture and Sports in the USSR in 1960-1985 Years. Bulletin Social-Economic and Humanitarian Research, Tom 14, Issue 16. Pp. 3 - 9. (In Engl).

Matveev L.P. (1991) Theory and methodology of physical culture (general foundations of the theory and methodology of physical education); theoretical and methodological aspects of sports and professionally applied culture. M.: Physical culture and sport. 543 p. (In Russ).

Nikolaev Y.M. (2000) Theory of physical culture: functional, value, activity, productive aspects. St. Petersburg: SPbGAFK named after P.F. Lesgaft. 80 p. (In Russ).

Seliverstova D.N., Seliverstova V.V. (1994) Methods and techniques for improving the physical condition of students with health disorders. Volgograd: Change. 56 p. (In Russ).

Smirnov B.I. (1965) Individual differences in the manifestation of determination and courage among gymnasts due to the peculiarities of their temperament. Psychological preparation of an athlete: A collection of scientific papers. M.: Physical culture and sport. Pp. 51-58. (In Russ).

Stroeveva I.V., Dorokhov R.N., Guba V.P. (1999) Development of a complex for determining strength and speed-strength indicators in children and young athletes. Scientific works of VNIIFK. M.: VNIIFK. Pp. 180-185. (In Russ).

Suleymanov I.I. (1988) Physical education for everyone. Omsk: Publishing House. 75 p. (In Russ).

Visitei N.N. (1989) Physical culture of the individual (problems of human physicality: methodological, socio-philosophical, pedagogical aspects). Chisinau: Shtinitsa. 110 p. (In Russ).

Volkov V.Yu., Volkova L.M., Polovnikov P.V. (1999) Physical culture. Course of lectures: St. Petersburg: Nestor. 146 p. (In Russ).

Vydrin V.M. (1988) Theory of physical culture (cultural aspect). L.: GDOIFK named after P.F. Lesgaft. 45 p. (In Russ).

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПОДГОТОВКИ СТУДЕНТОВ В ОБЛАСТИ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ И СПОРТА В ТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ ВУЗАХ РОССИИ: ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ

Лубкин Янис Янович¹, Никифорова Любовь Александровна², Ермолова Елена
Анатольевна³, Груза Мария Сергеевна⁴, Балакари Татьяна Михайловна⁵

¹Старший преподаватель, Воронежский государственный технический университет,
ул. 20-летия Октября 84, Воронеж, Россия, E-mail: ia.iani4@yandex.ru

²Старший Преподаватель, Воронежский государственный технический университет,
ул. 20-летия Октября 84, Воронеж, Россия, E-mail: nikiforovala@inbox.ru

³Старший преподаватель, Воронежский государственный технический университет, ул. 20-
летия Октября 84, Воронеж, Россия, E-mail: fizcult_kaf@vgasu.vrn.ru

⁴Старший преподаватель, Воронежский государственный технический университет,
ул. 20-летия Октября 84, Воронеж, Россия, E-mail: mgruza@yandex.ru

⁵Старший преподаватель, Воронежский государственный технический университет,
ул. 20-летия Октября 84, Воронеж, Россия, E-mail: malya.tanya@mail.ru

Аннотация

В статье рассматривается система высшего профессионального образования в сфере физической культуры и спорта, которая далеко не в состоянии в полной мере обеспечить экономику специалистами, способными эффективно осуществлять профессиональную деятельность в рыночных условиях. Специалисты после окончания вуза должны обладать не только фундаментальными разносторонними знаниями, навыками и умениями в профессиональной сфере, но и комплексом устойчивых свойств, определяющих пригодность к профессиональной деятельности и отвечающих требованиям современного производства, таких как стрессоустойчивость, конкурентоспособность, высокая работоспособность, самооборона, здоровье и диапазон функциональных возможностей организма. Именно эти качества можно сформировать в процессе физического воспитания, так как при занятиях спортом создаются ситуации, заставляющие действовать более осмысленно и сдержанно.

Ключевые слова: спорт, образование, студент, вуз, история, страна.

СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

Andrews, D.K. (1993) The role of education in promoting a healthy lifestyle in the twenty-first century. Theory and practice of physical culture. Number 1. Pp. 46-48. (In Russ).

Balsevich V.K. (1988) Physical culture for everyone and for everyone. M.: Physical culture and sport. 208 p. (In Russ).

Cherkashin V.P. (2000) Individualization of the training process of young athletes in speed and power athletics: Monograph: VGAFK. 240 p. (In Russ).

Erofeeva T.M. (1995) Physical culture in the educational process of the university. Physical culture: upbringing, education, training. Pp. 27-35. (In Russ).

Ershov B.A., Lubkin Y.Y. (2016) The activities of the Russian Orthodox Church in countering extremism and terrorism in modern Russia. Historical, philosophical, political and legal sciences, cultural studies and art history. Questions of theory and practice. Vol. 11-2 (73). Pp. 97-99. (In Russ).

Ershov B.A., Nebolsin V.A., Solovieva S.R. (2020) Higher education in technical universities of Russia. 7th International conference on education and social sciences. Abstracts Proceedings. Pp. 55-58. (In Engl).

Ershov B.A., Perepelitsyn A., Glazkov E., Volkov I., Volkov S. (2019) Church and state in Russia: management issues. 5th International conference on advances in education and social sciences. Abstracts & Proceedings, e-publication. Pp. 26-29. (In Engl).

Ershov B.A., Zhdanova T.A., Kashirsky S.N., Monko T. (2020) Education in the university as an important factor in the socialization of students in Russia. 6th International Conference on Advances in Education. Abstracts & Proceedings. Pp. 517-520. (In Engl).

Fomin Y.A., Vavilov Yu.I. (1991) Physiological foundations of motor activity. M.: Physical culture and sport. 224 p. (In Russ).

Fursov V.N., Ershov B.A., Lubkin Y.Y. (2016) The participation of the Russian Orthodox Church in the patriotic education of the young generation in modern Russia. News of the Voronezh State Pedagogical University. Vol. 1 (270). Pp. 147-150. (In Russ).

Gessen S.I. (1995) Worldview and education. Education and pedagogy of the Russian abroad. M. 105 p. (In Russ).

Gladkikh O.V., Ermolova E.A., Lukin A.A., Ermilova O.Y., Vasilyeva L.M. Physical Culture and Health-Improving Movement in the USSR in 1920-1930. Bulletin Social-Economic and Humanitarian Research. Tom 12, Issue 14. Pp. 37 - 43. (In Engl).

Gruga M.S., Vyalykh N.N., Dushkin O.A., Shcherbina I.V., Nikiforova L.A. (2022) Historical aspects of sports-mass work in higher educational institutions of Russia. Bulletin Social-Economic and Humanitarian Research. Vol. 13 (15). Pp. 3-9. (In Engl).

Ignatiev A.S., Lotonenko A.V. (1999) Theoretical and methodological aspects of physical culture of students. Voronezh. 168 p. (In Russ).

Jusudov V.P. (2000) Motor modes in the rehabilitation system: A manual on physical therapy for students of the faculty, stomatol. fac. and fac. sports. medicine. St. Petersburg. 115 p. (In Russ).

Kuramshin Yu.F. (1996) Higher sports achievements as an object of system analysis. St. Petersburg: GAFK named after P.F. Lesgaft. 169 p. (In Russ).

Lubkin Y.Y., Novikov Y.N., Gostev V.N., Kutuzova I. A., Balakari T.M. (2022) The Development of Physical Culture and Sports in the USSR in 1960-1985 Years. Bulletin Social-Economic and Humanitarian Research, Tom 14, Issue 16. Pp. 3 - 9. (In Engl).

Matveev L.P. (1991) Theory and methodology of physical culture (general foundations of the theory and methodology of physical education); theoretical and methodological aspects of sports and professionally applied culture. M.: Physical culture and sport. 543 p. (In Russ).

Nikolaev Y.M. (2000) Theory of physical culture: functional, value, activity, productive aspects. St. Petersburg: SPbGAFK named after P.F. Lesgaft. 80 p. (In Russ).

Seliverstova D.N., Seliverstova V.V. (1994) Methods and techniques for improving the physical condition of students with health disorders. Volgograd: Change. 56 p. (In Russ).

Smirnov B.I. (1965) Individual differences in the manifestation of determination and courage among gymnasts due to the peculiarities of their temperament. Psychological preparation of an athlete: A collection of scientific papers. M.: Physical culture and sport. Pp. 51-58. (In Russ).

Stroeveva I.V., Dorokhov R.N., Guba V.P. (1999) Development of a complex for determining strength and speed-strength indicators in children and young athletes. Scientific works of VNIIFK. M.: VNIIFK. Pp. 180-185. (In Russ).

Suleymanov I.I. (1988) Physical education for everyone. Omsk: Publishing House. 75 p. (In Russ).

Visitei N.N. (1989) Physical culture of the individual (problems of human physicality: methodological, socio-philosophical, pedagogical aspects). Chisinau: Shtinitza. 110 p. (In Russ).

Volkov V.Yu., Volkova L.M., Polovnikov P.V. (1999) Physical culture. Course of lectures: St. Petersburg: Nestor. 146 p. (In Russ).

Vydrin V.M. (1988) Theory of physical culture (cultural aspect). L.: GDOIFK named after P.F. Lesgaft. 45 p. (In Russ).